

Electronic Supplementary Material for:
Distance functions of carabids in crop fields depend on functional traits, crop type and adjacent habitat: a synthesis

ESM 1: Supplementary tables and figures

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Search terms

Search terms used in the 'Web of Science' search (initial search conducted on 06.11.2018):

carabid* OR "ground beetle"

AND

"semi-natural habitat" OR "seminatural habitat" OR margin* OR
boundary OR strip OR "buffer strip" OR shelterbelt OR hedge* OR
border OR "field border" OR fringe OR "agri-environmental scheme" OR
"within-field distribution" OR "distance to edge" OR "field edge" OR
"field distribution" OR "spill-over" OR spillover

AND

"cropping system" OR field* OR crop* OR farmland OR agriculture OR
wheat OR arable OR maize OR "oilseed rape" OR Canola

AND

diversity OR "species richness" OR biodiversity OR abundance OR
density

Figure S1 Reported distance functions in the literature

FIGURE S1: Reported distance functions for carabid richness (A) and carabid activity density or abundance (B) in the publications detected as potentially suitable based on our literature search (44 publications) and by asking colleagues (15 publications). ‘Positive’ (red) and ‘negative’ (blue) indicate a significant increase or decrease reported in the publication, ‘no change’ (yellow) indicates no significant distance function was found, ‘contradicting patterns’ (violet) indicates that distance functions differed depending on the context within the same publication. For both richness and activity density, a majority of the publications did not report distance functions despite data being collected with a suitable design (‘not reported’; grey).

Figure S2 Map of crop types and adjacent habitat types in the datasets

FIGURE S2: Map of European countries from which datasets were used for the analyses (yellow colouration). Colouration of the points indicates the number of crop types (A) and adjacent habitat types in each dataset, (B). Points jittered by 0.5° to reduce overlay. For more information on the datasets, see Table S2.

Figure S3 Effect of trap days on carabid richness.

FIGURE S3: Marginal effect of carabid beetle richness across trap days (traps pooled per plot, see materials and methods; prediction derived from the model, see Table S5). The response curve on the left depicts predicted richness with 95% credible interval (CI). The density plot on the right shows the slope coefficient (on the log scale) of trap days with median (point) 66% (thick bars) and 95% (thin bars) posterior credible intervals. The value of 1, indicated with a vertical dashed line, corresponds to a perfectly flat slope, and parameters with 95% credible intervals falling entirely above or below 1 can be regarded as positive or negative slopes, respectively. The rug in the left panel indicates numbers of days for which data points were available, predictions are limited to the range of trapping days covered by the available data.

Figure S4 Overall predictions for omnivorous species

FIGURE S4: Overall marginal predictions for (A & B) the richness of omnivorous carabid species and (C & D) the activity density of omnivorous carabid species across the within field distance gradient both with all species included (A & C) and with the hyperdominant species *Poecilus cupreus* removed (B & D). Response curves depict posterior predictions with 50% (dark), 80% (medium) and 95% (light) credible intervals (CI), back-transformed from the log-link scale to response scale. The rug indicates distances for which data points were available, predictions are limited to the distances covered by the available data (not all data used in the models is shown; distance was clipped at 65 m for visualization as a majority of the data was available up to this distance). For statistics and values, see electronic supplementary material 1: tables S8 & S9.

Figure S5 Predictions for omnivorous species in relation to crop and adjacent habitat type

FIGURE S5: Overall marginal within-field distance slope coefficients for the richness and activity density of omnivorous carabid species in relation to crop type (left) and adjacent habitat type (right) both with all species included and with the hyperdominant species *Poecilus cupreus* removed. Slope coefficient estimates (median) of the posterior sample (black lines) with 50% (dark), 80% (medium) and 95% (light) credible intervals (CI), back-transformed from the log link scale to response scale. The dashed line represents the slope coefficient of 1, i.e. a flat slope. Coefficients can be interpreted as percent change in the response every 10 m towards the field centre. For statistics and values, see electronic supplementary material 1: tables S8 & S9.

Table S1 Publications returned by the literature search

Table S1: List papers obtained from the initial literature search in the ISI Web of Science Core Collection and deemed suitable after full text review. For all papers, data were requested from the authors. For exclusion reasons for the datasets received but ultimately not included, see exclusion criteria stated in the text and Table S3.

Reference	data received after request	data included after review
Al Hassan, D; Georgelin, E; Delattre, T; Burel, F; Plantegenest, M; Kindlmann, P; Butet, A (2013) Does the presence of grassy strips and landscape grain affect the spatial distribution of aphids and their carabid predators? <i>Agricultural and Forest Entomology</i> 15, 24-33.		
Anjum-Zubair, M; Schmidt-Entling, MH; Querner, P; Frank, T (2010) Influence of within-field position and adjoining habitat on carabid beetle assemblages in winter wheat. <i>Agricultural and Forest Entomology</i> 12, 301-306.	X	X
Bedford, SE; Usher, MB (1994) Distribution of arthropod species across the margins of farm woodlands. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 48, 295-305.		
Birkhofer, K; Fevrier, V; Heinrich, AE; Rink, K; Smith, HG (2018) The contribution of CAP greening measures to conservation biological control at two spatial scales. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 255, 84-94.		
Birkhofer, K; Wolters, V; Diekotter, T (2014) Grassy margins along organically managed cereal fields foster trait diversity and taxonomic distinctness of arthropod communities. <i>Insect Conservation and Diversity</i> 7, 274-287.	X	X
Chapelin-Viscardi, JD; Maillat-Mezeray, J; Tosser, V; Wartelle, R (2014) Emergence of Ground beetles in farming areas. Choice of habitat, diversity and specific requirements (Carabidae, Coleoptera). <i>Bulletin Mensuel de la Société Liméenne de Lyon</i> 83, 157-170.		
Cividanes, FJ; Araujo, ES; Ide, S; Galli, JC (2010) Distribution and habitat preference of Carabidae and Staphylinidae (Coleoptera) in an orange orchard and forest fragment. <i>Florida Entomologist</i> 93, 339-345.		
Cividanes, FJ; dos Santos-Cividanes, TM; Ferraudo, AS; da Matta, DH (2018) Edge effects on carabid beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae) between forest fragments and agricultural fields in south-east Brazil. <i>Austral Entomology</i> 57, 9-16.		
Collins, KL; Boatman, ND; Wilcox, A; Holland, JM; Chaney, K (2002) Influence of beetle banks on cereal, aphid predation in winter wheat. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 93, 337-350.		
Dennis, P; Fry, GLA (1992) Field margins – can they enhance natural enemy population-densities and general arthropod diversity on farmland? <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 40, 95-115.		
Ditner, N; Balmer, O; Beck, J; Blick, T; Nagel, P; Luka, H (2013) Effects of experimentally planting non-crop flowers into cabbage fields on the abundance and diversity of predators. <i>Biodiversity and Conservation</i> 22, 1049-1061.	X	X
Ernoult, A; Vialatte, A; Butet, A; Michel, N; Rantier, Y; Jambon, O; Burel, F (2013) Grassy strips in their landscape context, their role as new habitat for biodiversity. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 166, 15-27.		
Fernandes M, Ivan C; Cividanes, FJ; Ide, S; Haddad, GQ (2012) Diversity and habitat preferences of Carabidae and Staphylinidae (Coleoptera) in two agroecosystems. <i>Bragantia</i> 71.		
Ferrante, M; Gonzalez, E; Lövei, GL (2017) Predators do not spill over from forest fragments to maize fields in a landscape mosaic in central Argentina. <i>Ecology and Evolution</i> 7, 7699-7707.	X	
Fournier, E; Loreau, M (1999) Effects of newly planted hedges on ground-beetle diversity (Coleoptera, Carabidae) in an agricultural landscape. <i>Ecography</i> 22, 87-97.		
Fournier, E; Loreau, M (2002) Foraging activity of the carabid beetle <i>Pterostichus melanarius</i> Ill. in field margin habitats. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 89, 253-259.		

Frank, T (1997) Species diversity of ground beetles (Carabidae) in sown weed strips and adjacent fields. <i>Biological Agriculture & Horticulture</i> 15, 297-307.		
French, BW; Elliott, NC (1999) Temporal and spatial distribution of ground beetle (Coleoptera : Carabidae) assemblages in grasslands and adjacent wheat fields. <i>Pedobiologia</i> 43, 73-84.	X (2 datasets)	
García, AF; Griffiths, GJK; Thomas, CFG (2000) Density, distribution and dispersal of the carabid beetle <i>Nebria brevicollis</i> in two adjacent cereal fields. <i>Annals of Applied Biology</i> 137, 89-97.		
Hassal, M; Hawthorne, A; Maudsley, M; White, P; Cardwell, C (1992) Effects of headland management on invertebrate communities in cereal fields. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 40, 155-178.		
Hawthorne, AJ; Hassall, M; Sotherton, NW (1998) Effects of cereal headland treatments on the abundance and movements of three species of carabid beetles. <i>Applied Soil Ecology</i> 9, 417-422.		
Hof, AR; Bright, PW (2010) The impact of grassy field margins on macro-invertebrate abundance in adjacent arable fields. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 139, 280-283.	X	X
Kagawa, Y; Maeto, K (2009) Spatial population structure of the predatory ground beetle <i>Carabus yaconinus</i> (Coleoptera: Carabidae) in the mixed farmland-woodland satoyama landscape of Japan. <i>European Journal of Entomology</i> 106, 385-391.		
Kagawa, Y; Maeto, K (2014) Ground beetle (Coleoptera: Carabidae) assemblages associated with a satoyama landscape in Japan: the effects of soil moisture, weed height, and distance from woodlands. <i>Applied Entomology and Zoology</i> 49, 429-436.		
Kajak, A; Oleszczuk, M (2004) Effect of shelterbelts on adjoining cultivated fields: Patrolling intensity of carabid beetles (Carabidae) and spiders (Araneae). <i>Polish Journal of Ecology</i> 52, 155-172.		
Kujawa, K; Sobczyk, D; Kajak, A (2006) Dispersal of <i>Harpalus rufipes</i> (Degeer)(Carabidae) between shelterbelt and cereal field. <i>Polish Journal of Ecology</i> 54, 243-252.	X	
Labruyere, Sarah; Petit, Sandrine; Ricci, Benoit (2018) Annual variation of oilseed rape habitat quality and role of grassy field margins for seed eating carabids in arable mosaics. <i>Agricultural and Forest Entomology</i> 20, 234-245.		
Lee, JC; Menalled, FB; Landis, DA (2001) Refuge habitats modify impact of insecticide disturbance on carabid beetle communities. <i>Journal of Applied Ecology</i> 38, 472-483.		
Lys, JA; Zimmermann, M; Nentwig, W (1994) Increase in activity density and species number of carabid beetles in cereals as a result of strip-management. <i>Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata</i> 73, 1-9.		
Madeira, F; Tschamtkke, T; Elek, Z; Kormann, UG; Pons, X; Rosch, V; Samu, F; Scherber, C; Batary, P (2016) Spillover of arthropods from cropland to protected calcareous grassland - the neighbouring habitat matters. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 235, 127-133.	X	X
Marasas, ME; Sarandon, SJ; Cicchino, A (2010) Semi-Natural Habitats and Field Margins in a Typical Agroecosystem of the Argentinean Pampas as a Reservoir of Carabid Beetles. <i>Journal of Sustainable Agriculture</i> 34, 153-168.		
Marrec, R; Badenhauer, I; Bretagnolle, V; Borger, L; Roncoroni, M; Guillon, N; Gauffre, B (2015) Crop succession and habitat preferences drive the distribution and abundance of carabid beetles in an agricultural landscape. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 199, 282-289.	X (3 datasets)	X (3 datasets)
Nash, MA; Thomson, LJ; Hoffmann, AA (2008) Effect of remnant vegetation, pesticides, and farm management on abundance of the beneficial predator <i>Notonomus gravis</i> (Chaudoir) (Coleoptera : Carabidae). <i>Biological Control</i> 46, 83-93.	X	
Ng, K; Barton, PS; Macfadyen, S; Lindenmayer, DB; Driscoll, DA (2018) Beetle's responses to edges in fragmented landscapes are driven by adjacent farmland use, season and cross-habitat movement. <i>Landscape Ecology</i> 33, 109-125.	X	
Outward, R; Sorenson, CE; Bradley, JR (2008) Effects of vegetated field borders on arthropods in cotton fields in eastern North Carolina. <i>Journal of Insect Science</i> 8.		

Rouabah, A; Villerd, J; Amiaud, B; Plantureux, S; Lasserre-Joulin, F (2015) Response of carabid beetles diversity and size distribution to the vegetation structure within differently managed field margins. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 200, 21-32.		
Roume, A; Ouin, A; Raison, L; Deconchat, M (2011) Abundance and species richness of overwintering ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae) are higher in the edge than in the centre of a woodlot. <i>European Journal of Entomology</i> 108, 615-622.		
Saska, P; Vodde, M; Heijerman, T; Westerman, P; van der Werf, W (2007) The significance of a grassy field boundary for the spatial distribution of carabids within two cereal fields. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 122, 427-434.	X	
Soboleva-Dokuchaeva, II; Chernyshev, VB; Afonina, VM; Ovchinnikova, MF; Timokhov, AV (2000) Factors responsible for distribution of ground beetles (Coleoptera, Carabidae) in agricultural lands. <i>Zoologicheskii Zhurnal</i> 79, 1071-1072.		
Soboleva-Dokuchaeva, II; Tshernyshev, VB; Afonina, VM; Timokhov, AV (2000) Seasonal dynamics of spatial distribution of mass ground-beetle species (Coleoptera, Carabidae) in agroecosystems of the mixed forest zone. <i>Zoologicheskii Zhurnal</i> 79, 822-823.		
Sutter, L; Amato, M; Jeanneret, P; Albrecht, M (2018) Overwintering of pollen beetles and their predators in oilseed rape and semi-natural habitats. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 265, 275-281.	X	X
Thomas, CFG; Green, F; Marshall, EJP (1997) Distribution, dispersal and population size of the ground beetles, <i>Pterostichus melanarius</i> (Illiger) and <i>Harpalus rufipes</i> (Degeer) (Coleoptera, carabidae), in field margin habitats. <i>Biological Agriculture & Horticulture</i> 15, 337-352.		
Thomas, CFG; Marshall, EJP (1999) Arthropod abundance and diversity in differently vegetated margins of arable fields. <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment</i> 72, 131-144.		
Van Vooren, L; Reubens, B; Ampoorter, E; Broekx, S; Pardon, P; Van Waes, C; Verheyen, K (2018) Monitoring the Impact of Hedgerows and Grass Strips on the Performance of Multiple Ecosystem Service Indicators. <i>Environmental Management</i> 62, 241-259.	X	X
Total	18	11

Table S2 Datasets included in the analyses

Study ID	country	region	year	months	crop types	adjacent habitat classes	study sites	maximal distance [m]	trapping days	reference
Bata01	Germany	Lower Saxony	2011	July / August	cereals	herbaceous	7	10	14	Madeira <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Bata02	Germany	Lower Saxony	2008	June	cereals	herbaceous	18	30	35	Batáry <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Bata03	Germany	Lower Saxony	2013	June	cereals	herbaceous	36	200	28	Batáry <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Birk01	Germany	Lower Saxony	2008	June / July	cereals	herbaceous	17	40	14	Birkhofer, Wolters and Diekötter (2014)
Boet01	Germany	Lower Frankonia	2016	April – July	oilseed crops	herbaceous, control	31	65	252	Boetzl <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Boet02	Germany	Lower Frankonia	2017	April – July	cereals	herbaceous, control	30	65	252	Boetzl <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Entl01	Switzerland	Solothurn	2005	May / June	cereals	herbaceous	20	30	48	Anjum-Zubair <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Farm01	France	Armorique	2013 / 2014	May – July	cereals, maize	herbaceous, woody	104	25	16	Sirami <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Farm02	France	Camargue	2013 / 2014	May – July	cereals	herbaceous, woody	17	25	16	Sirami <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Farm03	France	Coteaux	2013 / 2014	May – July	cereals, maize, leguminous crops, oilseed crops	herbaceous, woody, control	84	25	16	Sirami <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Farm04	UK	EastAnglia	2012 / 2013	May – July	cereals, maize, oilseed crops, vegetables	herbaceous, woody	150	25	16	Sirami <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Farm05	Germany	Lower Saxony	2013 / 2014	May – July	cereals, oilseed crops	herbaceous, control	154	25	16	Sirami <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Farm06	Spain	Catalonia	2013 / 2014	April – June	cereals	herbaceous, woody, control	34	25	16	Sirami <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Farm08	France	Nouvelle-Aquitaine	2013 / 2014	May – July	cereals, maize, leguminous crops, oilseed crops	herbaceous, woody, control	249	25	16	Sirami <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Hof01	UK	Berkshire	2009	May – July	cereals	herbaceous, woody	32	20	15	Hof and Bright (2010)
Knap01	Czech Republic	Central Bohemia	2013	June / July	cereals, oilseed crops	herbaceous, woody	4	20	114	Knapp <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Luka01	Switzerland	Aargau	2010	June – September	vegetables	herbaceous	7	20	70	Ditner <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Luka02	Switzerland	Aargau	1996 – 1998	May – July	cereals	herbaceous	3	70	280	Pfiffner and Luka (2003)
Maas01	Austria	Lower Austria	2017	April / May	cereals	herbaceous	5	157.5	21	Maas <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Maas02	Austria	Lower Austria	2018	April / May	cereals	herbaceous	5	157.5	21	Maas <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Maas03	Austria	Lower Austria	2019	April / May	cereals	herbaceous	5	157.5	21	Maas <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Marr01	France	Nouvelle-Aquitaine	2011 – 2013	April – July	cereals, leguminous crops, oilseed crops	herbaceous, woody	38	94	18	Marrec <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Marr02	France	Armorique	2010 / 2011	April – July	cereals, leguminous crops, oilseed crops	herbaceous, woody	49	143	28	Marrec <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Marr03	France	Gascogne	2010 – 2012	April – July	cereals, leguminous crops, oilseed crops	herbaceous, woody	37	97	11	Marrec <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Schi01	Germany	Palatinate	2014	May / June	vegetables	herbaceous, woody, control	17	26	14	Fusser <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Sutt01	Switzerland	Zuerich	2014	April / May	oilseed crops	herbaceous, woody, control	18	25	28	Sutter <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Tsch01	Switzerland	Zuerich	2012	May – July	cereals	herbaceous, control	25	25	42	Tschumi <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Voor01	Belgium	North Flanders & Heuveland	2014	May / June	cereals	herbaceous, woody	8	30	42	Van Vooren <i>et al.</i> (2018)

Table S3 Datasets excluded from the analyses

Table S3: List of all datasets excluded from our analyses with country, region, study years, crop types, adjacent habitat types, study sites, maximal sampled distances [m] and sampling days included in the datasets. Exclusion reason is highlighted in red. Datasets marked with ‘**’ do not contain species level IDs.

Study ID	country	region	year	months	crop types	adjacent habitat classes	study sites	maximal distance [m]	trapping days (per trap)	reference
Bade01	France	Nouvelle-Aquitaine	2015	July	oilseed crops	herbaceous	23	45	4	Badenhausser <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Cutl01*	Canada	Nova Scotia	2008 / 2009	May – August	blueberry	woody	4	25	24 – 36	Cutler <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Cutl02*	Canada	Nova Scotia	2017	‘summer’	blueberry	woody	6	160	21	Loureiro A (2018)
Farm07	Canada	Ontario	2013 / 2014	April – June	cereals, leguminous crops, vegetables	herbaceous, woody, control	238	25	16	Sirami <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Fren01	USA	Oklahoma	1993 - 1996	various	cereals	herbaceous	6	50	203 – 237	French <i>et al.</i> (1999)
Fren02	USA	Oklahoma	1995 / 1996	various	cereals	herbaceous	9	50	68 – 410	French <i>et al.</i> (2001)
Gonz01	Argentina	Cordoba	2011 / 2012	December - February	leguminous crops	woody	9	100	7	González <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Juch01	Poland	Zachodniopomorskie	2018	June – September	vegetables	herbaceous	1	29	69	?
Koiv01	Finland	Kanta-Häme	2001	May – August	vegetables	woody	2	30	66	Koivula <i>et al.</i> (2004)
Mart01	South Korea	Gangwon-do	2009	June – September	leguminous crops, vegetables	herbaceous	28	20	20	Martin <i>et al.</i> (2016)
Nash01	Australia	Victoria	2006	February / March	forage grass	herbaceous	20	200	32	Nash <i>et al.</i> (2008)
Ng01	Australia	New South Wales	2014 / 2015	September / October January / February	cereals	woody	11	200	28	Ng <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Sask01	Netherlands	Gelderland	2004	March – July	cereals	herbaceous	2	49	146	Saska <i>et al.</i> (2007)

Table S4 Study sites per crop type and adjacent habitat.

Table S4: Study sites per crop type and adjacent habitat type.

Crop type	Adjacent habitat type	Number of sites
cereals	none	160
	herbaceous	399
	woody	207
maize	none	12
	herbaceous	8
	woody	58
oilseed crops	none	62
	herbaceous	109
	woody	52
vegetables	none	7
	herbaceous	22
	woody	22
leguminous crops	none	23
	herbaceous	16
	woody	37

Table S5 Carabid beetle species and their traits.

Table S5: The 241 carabid species contained in the accumulated dataset with total number of individuals, number of study sites on which the species occur as well as their (predominant) diet and mean body size. Carabids not identified to species level were excluded in this table. Carabid beetle traits were obtained from the database carabids.org (Homburg et al. 2014), monographies as well as previous studies on carabid beetle functional traits (Hürka 1996; Ribera et al. 2001; Pakeman & Stockan 2014; Hanson et al. 2016).

Species	total individuals	number of sampling plots with occurrence	diet	mean body size [mm]
<i>Abax ovalis</i>	5	4	carnivorous	13
<i>Abax parallelepipedus</i>	81	58	carnivorous	19
<i>Abax parallelus</i>	37	19	carnivorous	15.5
<i>Acupalpus elegans</i>	9	4	omnivorous	3.5
<i>Acupalpus interstitialis</i>	5	5	omnivorous	2.5
<i>Acupalpus meridianus</i>	354	150	omnivorous	3.5
<i>Agonum emarginatum</i>	7	7	carnivorous	8
<i>Agonum gracilipes</i>	1	1	carnivorous	7.5
<i>Agonum lugens</i>	6	5	carnivorous	8.5
<i>Agonum micans</i>	4	3	carnivorous	6
<i>Agonum muelleri</i>	4982	462	carnivorous	7.5
<i>Agonum nigrum</i>	10	8	carnivorous	7
<i>Agonum sexpunctatum</i>	200	132	carnivorous	7.5
<i>Agonum viduum</i>	10	8	carnivorous	8
<i>Agonum viridicupreum</i>	5	2	carnivorous	8.5
<i>Amara aenea</i>	741	381	granivorous	7
<i>Amara anthobia</i>	2	2	granivorous	6
<i>Amara apricaria</i>	24	18	granivorous	7.5
<i>Amara aulica</i>	87	33	granivorous	12.5
<i>Amara bifrons</i>	59	28	granivorous	6
<i>Amara communis</i>	37	26	granivorous	6
<i>Amara consularis</i>	347	79	granivorous	8
<i>Amara convexior</i>	78	43	granivorous	8
<i>Amara eurynota</i>	283	73	granivorous	11
<i>Amara familiaris</i>	487	185	granivorous	7
<i>Amara fulva</i>	6	4	granivorous	9
<i>Amara littorea</i>	35	22	granivorous	7.5
<i>Amara lucida</i>	4	3	granivorous	5
<i>Amara lunicollis</i>	74	56	granivorous	7.5
<i>Amara montivaga</i>	29	20	granivorous	8
<i>Amara nitida</i>	1	1	granivorous	8
<i>Amara ovata</i>	17049	470	granivorous	8.5
<i>Amara plebeja</i>	308	127	granivorous	7
<i>Amara rufipes</i>	4	4	granivorous	8.5
<i>Amara sabulosa</i>	2	2	granivorous	5.5
<i>Amara similata</i>	4417	438	granivorous	8.5
<i>Amara tricuspidata</i>	2	2	granivorous	7.5
<i>Amblystomus niger</i>	1	1	granivorous	2.5
<i>Anchomenus dorsalis</i>	78281	1816	carnivorous	6.5
<i>Anisodactylus binotatus</i>	544	189	granivorous	10.5
<i>Anisodactylus poeciloides</i>	1	1	granivorous	11.5

<i>Anisodactylus signatus</i>	46	25	omnivorous	12
<i>Asaphidion flavipes</i>	698	330	carnivorous	3.5
<i>Asaphidion stierlini</i>	14	11	carnivorous	3.5
<i>Badister bullatus</i>	434	161	carnivorous	5
<i>Badister lacertosus</i>	40	18	carnivorous	6.5
<i>Badister meridionalis</i>	2	2	carnivorous	6.5
<i>Badister sodalis</i>	519	123	carnivorous	3.5
<i>Badister unipustulatus</i>	2	2	carnivorous	8
<i>Bembidion biguttatum</i>	42	8	carnivorous	3.5
<i>Bembidion deletum</i>	1	1	carnivorous	4.5
<i>Bembidion femoratum</i>	63	17	carnivorous	4.5
<i>Bembidion guttula</i>	129	32	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Bembidion iricolor</i>	11	5	carnivorous	4
<i>Bembidion lampros</i>	9074	1192	carnivorous	3
<i>Bembidion latinum</i>	1	1	carnivorous	5
<i>Bembidion lunulatum</i>	1174	78	carnivorous	3.5
<i>Bembidion mannerheimii</i>	1	1	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Bembidion normannum</i>	1	1	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Bembidion obtusum</i>	7700	606	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Bembidion properans</i>	872	161	carnivorous	3.5
<i>Bembidion quadrimaculatum</i>	4767	211	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Bembidion tetracolum</i>	1839	399	carnivorous	5
<i>Blemus discus</i>	14	6	carnivorous	4.5
<i>Brachinus crepitans</i>	21921	353	carnivorous	8
<i>Brachinus elegans</i>	30	18	carnivorous	7.5
<i>Brachinus explodens</i>	1079	174	carnivorous	5.5
<i>Brachinus immaculicornis</i>	14	11	carnivorous	8.5
<i>Brachinus sclopeta</i>	2637	195	carnivorous	5.5
<i>Bradycellus caucasicus</i>	1	1	omnivorous	3.5
<i>Bradycellus harpalinus</i>	3	2	omnivorous	4
<i>Bradycellus verbasci</i>	5	96	omnivorous	4.5
<i>Brosicus cephalotes</i>	34	7	granivorous	21
<i>Calathus ambiguus</i>	80	17	carnivorous	10
<i>Calathus cinctus</i>	158	9	carnivorous	7.5
<i>Calathus erratus</i>	8	6	carnivorous	10
<i>Calathus fuscipes</i>	4872	267	carnivorous	12
<i>Calathus melanocephalus</i>	44	25	carnivorous	7.5
<i>Calathus rotundicollis</i>	1	1	carnivorous	9.5
<i>Callistus lunatus</i>	1	1	carnivorous	5.5
<i>Calosoma inquisitor</i>	4	99	carnivorous	21.5
<i>Calosoma maderae</i>	7	5	carnivorous	27.5
<i>Carabus auratus</i>	1326	251	carnivorous	23.5
<i>Carabus auronitens</i>	4	4	carnivorous	25.5
<i>Carabus cancellatus</i>	189	90	carnivorous	26
<i>Carabus convexus</i>	33	19	carnivorous	17
<i>Carabus coriaceus</i>	29	21	carnivorous	37
<i>Carabus germarii</i>	4	3	carnivorous	29.5
<i>Carabus granulatus</i>	671	164	carnivorous	21.5
<i>Carabus hortensis</i>	5	4	carnivorous	26
<i>Carabus intricatus</i>	4	3	carnivorous	31

<i>Carabus monilis</i>	375	45	carnivorous	24
<i>Carabus nemoralis</i>	102	53	carnivorous	23
<i>Carabus problematicus</i>	1	1	carnivorous	25
<i>Carabus purpurascens</i>	41	25	carnivorous	30
<i>Carabus ulrichii</i>	7	5	carnivorous	24.5
<i>Carabus violaceus</i>	159	158	carnivorous	30
<i>Carterus fulvipes</i>	4	3	granivorous	8
<i>Chlaenius chrysocephalus</i>	299	86	carnivorous	8.5
<i>Chlaenius decipiens</i>	7	4	carnivorous	11.5
<i>Chlaenius festivus</i>	34	6	carnivorous	15
<i>Chlaenius nigricornis</i>	9	7	carnivorous	11
<i>Chlaenius olivieri</i>	3	2	carnivorous	11
<i>Chlaenius tristis</i>	1	1	carnivorous	11.5
<i>Cicindela campestris</i>	4	3	carnivorous	12
<i>Clivina collaris</i>	16	11	carnivorous	4.5
<i>Clivina fossor</i>	1491	201	carnivorous	6
<i>Cychrus caraboides</i>	2	2	carnivorous	17
<i>Cylindera germanica</i>	3	2	carnivorous	9.5
<i>Cylindera paludosa</i>	1	1	carnivorous	10.5
<i>Demetrias atricapillus</i>	302	175	carnivorous	5
<i>Diachromus germanus</i>	58	31	granivorous	8.5
<i>Dixus capito</i>	26	3	granivorous	12.5
<i>Dixus clypeatus</i>	6	6	granivorous	10
<i>Dixus sphaerocephalus</i>	1	1	granivorous	6.5
<i>Dolichus halensis</i>	22	6	carnivorous	16.5
<i>Dromius quadrimaculatus</i>	56	96	carnivorous	5
<i>Dromius schneideri</i>	1	1	carnivorous	5.5
<i>Drypta dentata</i>	4	4	carnivorous	8
<i>Dyschirius globosus</i>	50	15	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Elaphrus uliginosus</i>	1	1	carnivorous	9
<i>Epaphius secalis</i>	416	38	carnivorous	3.5
<i>Gynandromorphus etruscus</i>	14	13	granivorous	10.5
<i>Harpalus affinis</i>	9406	909	granivorous	10
<i>Harpalus atratus</i>	76	21	granivorous	11.5
<i>Harpalus attenuatus</i>	3	3	granivorous	8.5
<i>Harpalus calceatus</i>	5	3	granivorous	12.5
<i>Harpalus cupreus</i>	18	12	granivorous	12.5
<i>Harpalus dimidiatus</i>	1272	374	granivorous	12.5
<i>Harpalus distinguendus</i>	1725	376	granivorous	9
<i>Harpalus flavescens</i>	2	2	granivorous	12
<i>Harpalus griseus</i>	18	12	omnivorous	10
<i>Harpalus honestus</i>	4	3	granivorous	8.5
<i>Harpalus laevipes</i>	5	4	granivorous	10.5
<i>Harpalus latus</i>	152	107	granivorous	9.5
<i>Harpalus luteicornis</i>	267	111	granivorous	6.5
<i>Harpalus marginellus</i>	1	1	granivorous	10
<i>Harpalus oblitus</i>	40	31	granivorous	9.5
<i>Harpalus politus</i>	1	1	granivorous	9.5
<i>Harpalus pumilus</i>	1	1	granivorous	5
<i>Harpalus rubripes</i>	154	98	granivorous	10

<i>Harpalus rufipes</i>	10163	1242	granivorous	13.5
<i>Harpalus serripes</i>	61	18	granivorous	10.5
<i>Harpalus signaticornis</i>	716	141	granivorous	6.5
<i>Harpalus smaragdinus</i>	2	1	granivorous	9.5
<i>Harpalus subcylindricus</i>	10	7	granivorous	6.5
<i>Harpalus sulphuripes</i>	3	3	granivorous	7
<i>Harpalus tardus</i>	180	92	carnivorous	9
<i>Harpalus tenebrosus</i>	2	1	granivorous	9
<i>Laemostenus terricola</i>	1	1	carnivorous	14
<i>Leistus ferrugineus</i>	78	37	carnivorous	6.5
<i>Leistus fulvibarbis</i>	3	3	carnivorous	7.5
<i>Leistus rufomarginatus</i>	7	7	carnivorous	8
<i>Leistus spinibarbis</i>	22	12	carnivorous	8.5
<i>Licinus depressus</i>	2	2	carnivorous	10
<i>Licinus punctatulus</i>	1	1	carnivorous	15
<i>Limodromus assimilis</i>	465	147	carnivorous	11.5
<i>Loricera pilicornis</i>	3076	767	carnivorous	7
<i>Microlestes luctuosus</i>	8	5	carnivorous	2
<i>Microlestes maurus</i>	309	119	carnivorous	2
<i>Microlestes minutulus</i>	265	123	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Microlestes negrita</i>	3	3	carnivorous	2
<i>Molops elatus</i>	33	6	carnivorous	15
<i>Molops piceus</i>	16	16	carnivorous	11.5
<i>Nebria brevicollis</i>	1517	461	carnivorous	11.5
<i>Nebria salina</i>	5303	547	carnivorous	11
<i>Notiophilus aestuans</i>	334	137	carnivorous	4.5
<i>Notiophilus aquaticus</i>	6	6	carnivorous	5
<i>Notiophilus biguttatus</i>	2315	361	carnivorous	4.5
<i>Notiophilus germinyi</i>	63	34	carnivorous	5
<i>Notiophilus palustris</i>	235	135	carnivorous	5
<i>Notiophilus quadripunctatus</i>	150	112	carnivorous	4
<i>Notiophilus rufipes</i>	4	4	carnivorous	5
<i>Notiophilus substriatus</i>	32	31	carnivorous	4.5
<i>Ocys harpaloides</i>	2	97	carnivorous	5
<i>Olisthopus rotundatus</i>	1	1	carnivorous	6.5
<i>Ophonus ardosiacus</i>	148	40	granivorous	12
<i>Ophonus azureus</i>	310	137	granivorous	7.5
<i>Ophonus diffinis</i>	2	2	granivorous	11
<i>Ophonus laticollis</i>	52	21	granivorous	9.5
<i>Ophonus puncticeps</i>	19	16	granivorous	8
<i>Ophonus puncticollis</i>	1	1	granivorous	8
<i>Ophonus rufibarbis</i>	23	14	granivorous	7.5
<i>Ophonus rupicola</i>	4	4	granivorous	8
<i>Ophonus sabulicola</i>	4	4	granivorous	15
<i>Ophonus schaubergerianus</i>	26	12	granivorous	8.5
<i>Ophonus subquadratus</i>	3	2	granivorous	7
<i>Orthomus expansus</i>	7	6	carnivorous	10
<i>Oxypselaphus obscurus</i>	9	7	carnivorous	5
<i>Panagaeus bipustulatus</i>	24	15	omnivorous	7
<i>Panagaeus cruxmajor</i>	2	1	omnivorous	8

<i>Paradromius linearis</i>	4	3	carnivorous	4.5
<i>Paranchus albipes</i>	3	3	carnivorous	7.5
<i>Parophonus maculicornis</i>	11	9	granivorous	6
<i>Parophonus mendax</i>	16	16	granivorous	8
<i>Patrobus atrorufus</i>	40	8	carnivorous	8.5
<i>Pedius longicollis</i>	74	27	carnivorous	6
<i>Philorhizus melanocephalus</i>	1	1	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Philorhizus notatus</i>	2	2	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Poecilus cupreus</i>	65826	1651	omnivorous	11
<i>Poecilus gisellae</i>	1	1	carnivorous	9.5
<i>Poecilus lepidus</i>	45	22	carnivorous	12
<i>Poecilus puncticollis</i>	3	2	carnivorous	9
<i>Poecilus purpurascens</i>	27	21	carnivorous	10
<i>Poecilus versicolor</i>	1000	147	carnivorous	10
<i>Polistichus connexus</i>	6	6	carnivorous	8
<i>Porotachys bisulcatus</i>	1	1	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Pterostichus anthracinus</i>	2976	48	carnivorous	10.5
<i>Pterostichus burmeisteri</i>	12	12	carnivorous	13.5
<i>Pterostichus diligens</i>	2	2	carnivorous	5
<i>Pterostichus macer</i>	160	53	carnivorous	13
<i>Pterostichus madidus</i>	3872	325	carnivorous	16.5
<i>Pterostichus melanarius</i>	37257	1330	carnivorous	15
<i>Pterostichus melas</i>	30	9	carnivorous	16
<i>Pterostichus niger</i>	764	127	carnivorous	18.5
<i>Pterostichus nigrita</i>	40	105	carnivorous	10
<i>Pterostichus oblongopunctatus</i>	35	25	carnivorous	10.5
<i>Pterostichus ovoideus</i>	33	16	carnivorous	7
<i>Pterostichus pumilio</i>	1	1	carnivorous	5
<i>Pterostichus strenuus</i>	243	141	carnivorous	6
<i>Pterostichus vernalis</i>	1623	338	carnivorous	6.5
<i>Scybalicus oblongiusculus</i>	16	4	granivorous	11.5
<i>Sinechostictus stomoides</i>	2	2	carnivorous	5.5
<i>Stenolophus marginatus</i>	1	1	omnivorous	6.5
<i>Stenolophus mixtus</i>	1	1	carnivorous	5.5
<i>Stenolophus teutonius</i>	12	9	omnivorous	6
<i>Stomis benoiti</i>	1	1	carnivorous	10
<i>Stomis pumicatus</i>	169	86	carnivorous	7
<i>Syntomus foveatus</i>	33	22	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Syntomus obscuroguttatus</i>	166	88	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Syntomus truncatellus</i>	43	29	carnivorous	2.5
<i>Synuchus vivalis</i>	89	55	granivorous	7
<i>Tachys bistratus</i>	90	28	carnivorous	1.5
<i>Trechoblemus micros</i>	28	10	carnivorous	4.5
<i>Trechus obtusus</i>	10	105	carnivorous	3.5
<i>Trechus quadristriatus</i>	16780	818	carnivorous	3.5
<i>Trechus rubens</i>	23	15	carnivorous	5.5
<i>Trichotichnus laevicollis</i>	3	3	granivorous	7
<i>Trichotichnus nitens</i>	1	1	granivorous	8
<i>Zabrus tenebrioides</i>	141	62	granivorous	15
<i>Zuphium olens</i>	2	2	carnivorous	9.25

Table S6 Carabids according to diet and body-size

Table S6: Distribution of diet preferences and body-size classes among all carabid beetles identified to species level across all datasets, sites and plots.

	predominantly carnivorous species				omnivorous species				predominantly granivorous species				overall	
	species richness		individuals		species richness		individuals		species richness		individuals		species richness	individuals
	number	percentage	number	percentage	number	percentage	number	percentage	number	percentage	number	percentage		
small species (< 6 mm)	57	23.65	52,833	15.37	7	2.90	378	0.11	4	1.66	8	< 0.01	68	53,219
medium-sized species (6 - 10 mm)	50	20.75	114,245	33.25	5	2.07	57	0.02	50	20.75	36,813	10.71	105	151,115
large species (> 10 mm)	46	19.09	60,526	17.61	2	0.83	65,872	19.17	20	8.30	12,902	3.75	68	139,300
overall	153	63.49	227,604	66.23	14	5.81	66,307	19.30	74	30.71	49,723	14.47	241	343,634

Table S7 Model specifications for the calculated models

response	constant effect	varying effect	family
<i>richness (overall)</i>	distance log(trap days) crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Poisson (log)
<i>richness (predominantly carnivorous)</i>	distance log(trap days) crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Poisson (log)
<i>richness (omnivorous)</i> <i>[models with and without P. cupreus]</i>	distance log(trap days) crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Poisson (log)
<i>richness (predominantly granivorous)</i>	distance log(trap days) crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Poisson (log)
<i>activity density (overall)</i>	distance crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Gamma (log)
<i>activity density (predominantly carnivorous)</i>	distance crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Gamma (log)
<i>activity density (omnivorous)</i> <i>[models with and without P. cupreus]</i>	distance crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Gamma (log)
<i>activity density (predominantly granivorous)</i>	distance crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Gamma (log)
<i>activity density small species (< 6 mm)</i>	distance crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Gamma (log)
<i>activity density medium-sized species</i> <i>(6 - 10 mm)</i>	distance crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Gamma (log)
<i>activity density large species (> 10 mm)</i>	distance crop type adjacent habitat distance : crop type distance : adjacent habitat	1 + distance study/site	Gamma (log)

Table S8 Conditional model outputs

Table S8: Conditional model outputs for each response variable tested with estimate (median of the posterior sample), error (standard deviation of posterior sample), lower bound of the 95% credible interval (CI) and upper bound of the 95% credible interval (CI) for each of the constant (fixed) and varying (random) effects used.

response		parameter	estimate	95% CI lower bound	95% CI upper bound				
<i>richness (overall)</i>									
constant	slope	adj.control	0.973	0.947	0.998				
		adj.herb	0.971	0.954	0.985				
		adj.woody	0.961	0.937	0.984				
		crop.cereal	0.973	0.947	0.998				
		crop.legume	0.987	0.940	1.036				
		crop.maize	0.910	0.857	0.967				
		crop.oilseed	0.967	0.940	0.997				
		crop.vegetable	0.931	0.870	0.997				
		log.trap.days	1.048	1.033	1.063				
	intercept	adj.control	1.740	1.037	3.016				
		adj.herb	1.659	0.991	2.872				
		adj.woody	1.601	0.954	2.778				
		crop.cereal	1.740	1.037	3.016				
		crop.legume	1.606	0.937	2.796				
		crop.maize	1.481	0.871	2.579				
		crop.oilseed	2.185	1.299	3.829				
		crop.vegetable	1.728	1.005	3.014				
		varying	study	cor.intercept:distance	0.406	-0.452	0.963		
				sd.distance	0.167	0.046	0.333		
sd.intercept	0.535			0.398	0.732				
study:site	cor.intercept:distance		-0.297	-0.972	0.869				
	sd.distance		0.048	0.002	0.133				
	sd.intercept		0.245	0.219	0.272				
summary		R2	0.863	0.856	0.870				
<i>richness (predominantly carnivorous)</i>									
constant	slope	adj.control	0.991	0.961	1.022				
		adj.herb	0.980	0.962	0.993				
		adj.woody	0.963	0.936	0.987				
		crop.cereal	0.991	0.961	1.022				
		crop.legume	1.008	0.951	1.070				
		crop.maize	0.901	0.841	0.965				
		crop.oilseed	0.977	0.945	1.011				
		crop.vegetable	0.975	0.902	1.056				
		log.trap.days	1.039	1.022	1.055				
		intercept	adj.control	1.536	0.871	2.801			
			adj.herb	1.518	0.862	2.750			
			adj.woody	1.528	0.866	2.793			
			crop.cereal	1.536	0.871	2.801			
			crop.legume	1.209	0.668	2.234			
			crop.maize	1.222	0.686	2.248			
	crop.oilseed		1.626	0.912	2.973				
	crop.vegetable		1.463	0.805	2.782				
	varying		study	cor.intercept:distance	0.352	-0.733	0.969		
				sd.distance	0.120	0.007	0.304		
				sd.intercept	0.600	0.439	0.820		
			study:site	cor.intercept:distance	-0.039	-0.944	0.938		
				sd.distance	0.045	0.002	0.126		
				sd.intercept	0.209	0.178	0.242		
				summary		R2	0.808	0.796	0.819

richness (omnivorous)

constant	slope	adj.control	1.042	0.977	1.108	
		adj.herb	1.015	0.985	1.053	
		adj.woody	1.042	0.987	1.101	
		crop.cereal	1.042	0.977	1.108	
		crop.legume	1.020	0.919	1.130	
		crop.maize	1.131	1.000	1.275	
		crop.oilseed	1.013	0.940	1.088	
		crop.vegetable	1.015	0.874	1.178	
		log.trap.days	1.049	1.021	1.075	
		intercept	adj.control	0.133	0.053	0.361
			adj.herb	0.133	0.054	0.358
			adj.woody	0.126	0.050	0.345
			crop.cereal	0.133	0.053	0.361
			crop.legume	0.163	0.062	0.458
			crop.maize	0.122	0.047	0.342
crop.oilseed	0.164		0.064	0.454		
crop.vegetable	0.069		0.022	0.234		
varying	study		cor.intercept:distance	-0.178	-0.979	0.912
			sd.distance	0.256	0.011	0.745
	study:site	sd.intercept	0.826	0.572	1.182	
		cor.intercept:distance	-0.162	-0.971	0.920	
summary		sd.distance	0.065	0.003	0.187	
		sd.intercept	0.027	0.001	0.077	
		R2	0.450	0.416	0.481	

richness (omnivorous – without P. cupreus)

constant	slope	adj.control	0.975	0.888	1.066	
		adj.herb	0.966	0.896	1.035	
		adj.woody	0.988	0.870	1.114	
		crop.cereal	0.975	0.888	1.066	
		crop.legume	0.955	0.809	1.122	
		crop.maize	1.012	0.862	1.193	
		crop.oilseed	0.908	0.794	1.035	
		crop.vegetable	0.954	0.809	1.126	
		log.trap.days	1.112	1.066	1.155	
		intercept	adj.control	0.002	0.000	0.012
			adj.herb	0.002	0.000	0.012
			adj.woody	0.002	0.001	0.012
			crop.cereal	0.002	0.000	0.012
			crop.legume	0.002	0.000	0.016
			crop.maize	0.008	0.002	0.049
crop.oilseed	0.003		0.001	0.017		
crop.vegetable	0.003		0.000	0.020		
varying	study		cor.intercept:distance	0.064	-0.939	0.962
			sd.distance	0.364	0.013	1.117
	study:site	sd.intercept	1.059	0.609	1.794	
		cor.intercept:distance	-0.032	-0.954	0.945	
summary		sd.distance	0.339	0.012	0.943	
		sd.intercept	0.299	0.021	0.618	
		R2	0.263	0.196	0.340	

richness (predominantly granivorous)

constant	slope	adj.control	0.917	0.870	0.968	
		adj.herb	0.915	0.874	0.951	
		adj.woody	0.912	0.859	0.971	
		crop.cereal	0.917	0.870	0.968	
		crop.legume	0.953	0.873	1.034	
		crop.maize	0.870	0.775	0.980	
		crop.oilseed	0.955	0.899	1.018	
		crop.vegetable	0.879	0.782	0.988	
		log.trap.days	1.069	1.050	1.088	
		intercept	adj.control	0.219	0.113	0.430
			adj.herb	0.198	0.103	0.387
			adj.woody	0.174	0.090	0.339
	crop.cereal		0.219	0.113	0.430	
	crop.legume		0.253	0.128	0.502	
	crop.maize		0.216	0.107	0.434	
	crop.oilseed		0.406	0.212	0.806	
	varying	study	crop.vegetable	0.242	0.117	0.511
			cor.intercept:distance	0.189	-0.408	0.728
			sd.distance	0.714	0.371	1.151
study:site		sd.intercept	0.518	0.372	0.721	
		cor.intercept:distance	0.341	-0.774	0.978	
		sd.distance	0.117	0.005	0.283	
		sd.intercept	0.299	0.245	0.352	
		summary	R2	0.755	0.737	0.771

activity density (overall)

constant	slope	adj.control	1.037	0.986	1.085		
		adj.herb	0.996	0.971	1.021		
		adj.woody	1.035	0.995	1.078		
		crop.cereal	1.037	0.986	1.085		
		crop.legume	1.063	0.979	1.152		
		crop.maize	0.937	0.858	1.020		
		crop.oilseed	1.036	0.976	1.094		
		crop.vegetable	1.007	0.917	1.108		
		intercept	adj.control	1.845	1.181	2.788	
			adj.herb	1.810	1.187	2.703	
			adj.woody	1.762	1.153	2.717	
			crop.cereal	1.845	1.181	2.788	
			crop.legume	1.664	1.007	2.633	
			crop.maize	1.779	1.087	2.845	
			crop.oilseed	2.228	1.389	3.429	
	crop.vegetable		2.406	1.432	4.080		
	varying		study	cor.intercept:distance	0.172	-0.646	0.810
				sd.distance	0.300	0.029	0.576
		sd.intercept		1.053	0.799	1.400	
		study:site	cor.intercept:distance	-0.290	-0.964	0.825	
			sd.distance	0.101	0.004	0.284	
			sd.intercept	0.747	0.704	0.791	
			summary	R2	0.550	0.476	0.635

activity density (predominantly carnivorous)

constant	slope	adj.control	1.027	0.975	1.077	
		adj.herb	0.988	0.959	1.015	
		adj.woody	0.983	0.941	1.026	
		crop.cereal	1.027	0.975	1.077	
		crop.legume	1.041	0.953	1.134	
		crop.maize	0.941	0.859	1.032	
		crop.oilseed	1.036	0.975	1.098	
		crop.vegetable	1.021	0.922	1.129	
		intercept	adj.control	1.206	0.800	1.821
			adj.herb	1.262	0.855	1.871
			adj.woody	1.285	0.843	1.950
			crop.cereal	1.206	0.800	1.821
			crop.legume	0.975	0.614	1.581
			crop.maize	1.064	0.658	1.718
crop.oilseed	1.222		0.796	1.902		
varying	study	crop.vegetable	1.534	0.914	2.570	
		cor.intercept:distance	0.406	-0.383	0.929	
		sd.distance	0.360	0.049	0.702	
	study:site	sd.intercept	1.028	0.772	1.375	
		cor.intercept:distance	-0.211	-0.956	0.876	
		sd.distance	0.096	0.004	0.264	
		sd.intercept	0.730	0.684	0.777	
summary		R2	0.423	0.337	0.531	

activity density (omnivorous)

constant	slope	adj.control	1.083	1.008	1.161	
		adj.herb	1.056	0.999	1.121	
		adj.woody	1.171	1.079	1.264	
		crop.cereal	1.083	1.008	1.161	
		crop.legume	1.121	1.007	1.251	
		crop.maize	1.027	0.906	1.168	
		crop.oilseed	1.117	1.020	1.220	
		crop.vegetable	1.095	0.941	1.279	
		intercept	adj.control	0.410	0.258	0.659
			adj.herb	0.421	0.274	0.648
			adj.woody	0.298	0.185	0.482
			crop.cereal	0.410	0.258	0.659
			crop.legume	0.413	0.239	0.728
			crop.maize	0.291	0.167	0.515
crop.oilseed	0.385		0.233	0.637		
varying	study	crop.vegetable	0.394	0.173	0.889	
		cor.intercept:distance	-0.299	-0.719	0.207	
		sd.distance	0.998	0.627	1.505	
	study:site	sd.intercept	1.064	0.777	1.449	
		cor.intercept:distance	-0.202	-0.460	0.153	
		sd.distance	0.729	0.377	1.070	
		sd.intercept	0.815	0.746	0.887	
summary		R2	0.636	0.556	0.710	

activity density (omnivorous – without P. cupreus)

constant	slope	adj.control	1.026	0.944	1.120	
		adj.herb	0.981	0.925	1.044	
		adj.woody	1.029	0.920	1.149	
		crop.cereal	1.026	0.944	1.120	
		crop.legume	1.022	0.873	1.200	
		crop.maize	1.042	0.898	1.212	
		crop.oilseed	1.026	0.906	1.168	
		crop.vegetable	0.988	0.841	1.161	
		intercept	adj.control	0.062	0.036	0.106
			adj.herb	0.047	0.030	0.080
			adj.woody	0.053	0.029	0.103
			crop.cereal	0.062	0.036	0.106
			crop.legume	0.060	0.028	0.129
			crop.maize	0.077	0.037	0.161
			crop.oilseed	0.051	0.027	0.102
crop.vegetable	0.061		0.026	0.148		
varying	study		cor.intercept:distance	0.297	-0.782	0.972
		sd.distance	0.376	0.017	1.020	
		sd.intercept	0.807	0.531	1.223	
	study:site	cor.intercept:distance	-0.251	-0.960	0.874	
		sd.distance	0.297	0.011	0.881	
		sd.intercept	0.478	0.350	0.613	
summary		R2	0.579	0.502	0.656	

activity density (predominantly granivorous)

constant	slope	adj.control	0.931	0.890	0.976	
		adj.herb	0.964	0.939	0.986	
		adj.woody	0.954	0.913	0.998	
		crop.cereal	0.931	0.890	0.976	
		crop.legume	0.963	0.889	1.046	
		crop.maize	0.890	0.805	0.984	
		crop.oilseed	0.946	0.898	1.002	
		crop.vegetable	0.869	0.781	0.970	
		intercept	adj.control	0.283	0.214	0.377
			adj.herb	0.207	0.162	0.266
			adj.woody	0.208	0.158	0.278
			crop.cereal	0.283	0.214	0.377
			crop.legume	0.286	0.198	0.414
			crop.maize	0.402	0.273	0.593
			crop.oilseed	0.779	0.569	1.059
crop.vegetable	0.455		0.290	0.715		
varying	study		cor.intercept:distance	-0.098	-0.917	0.879
		sd.distance	0.133	0.005	0.441	
		sd.intercept	0.573	0.405	0.790	
	study:site	cor.intercept:distance	0.336	-0.752	0.970	
		sd.distance	0.147	0.006	0.372	
		sd.intercept	0.736	0.686	0.785	
summary		R2	0.429	0.371	0.495	

activity density of small species (< 6 mm)

constant	slope	adj.control	0.973	0.914	1.029	
		adj.herb	0.966	0.926	1.000	
		adj.woody	0.959	0.903	1.012	
		crop.cereal	0.973	0.914	1.029	
		crop.legume	0.979	0.884	1.085	
		crop.maize	0.877	0.789	0.972	
		crop.oilseed	0.998	0.928	1.072	
		crop.vegetable	0.965	0.867	1.076	
		intercept	adj.control	0.258	0.188	0.365
			adj.herb	0.263	0.198	0.353
			adj.woody	0.313	0.226	0.435
			crop.cereal	0.258	0.188	0.365
			crop.legume	0.243	0.161	0.378
			crop.maize	0.314	0.204	0.480
crop.oilseed	0.288		0.203	0.414		
varying	study	crop.vegetable	0.509	0.315	0.820	
		cor.intercept:distance	0.284	-0.317	0.799	
		sd.distance	0.532	0.160	0.962	
	study:site	sd.intercept	0.711	0.525	0.974	
		cor.intercept:distance	0.158	-0.850	0.949	
		sd.distance	0.156	0.006	0.427	
		sd.intercept	0.723	0.669	0.777	
summary		R2	0.188	0.116	0.298	

activity density of medium-sized species (6 – 10 mm)

constant	slope	adj.control	0.984	0.938	1.029	
		adj.herb	0.969	0.941	0.993	
		adj.woody	1.019	0.977	1.068	
		crop.cereal	0.984	0.938	1.029	
		crop.legume	0.939	0.862	1.020	
		crop.maize	0.993	0.897	1.096	
		crop.oilseed	0.983	0.931	1.037	
		crop.vegetable	0.941	0.842	1.055	
		intercept	adj.control	0.711	0.479	1.064
			adj.herb	0.686	0.468	1.015
			adj.woody	0.593	0.401	0.902
			crop.cereal	0.711	0.479	1.064
			crop.legume	0.617	0.389	1.000
			crop.maize	0.381	0.239	0.617
crop.oilseed	1.231		0.816	1.902		
varying	study	crop.vegetable	0.617	0.360	1.058	
		cor.intercept:distance	0.274	-0.686	0.937	
		sd.distance	0.242	0.014	0.594	
	study:site	sd.intercept	1.001	0.751	1.338	
		cor.intercept:distance	0.237	-0.838	0.957	
		sd.distance	0.114	0.005	0.315	
		sd.intercept	0.675	0.627	0.722	
summary		R2	0.410	0.339	0.500	

activity density of large species (> 10 mm)

constant	slope	adj.control	1.078	1.015	1.144	
		adj.herb	1.029	0.982	1.078	
		adj.woody	1.064	1.003	1.131	
		crop.cereal	1.078	1.015	1.144	
		crop.legume	1.112	1.013	1.222	
		crop.maize	0.998	0.897	1.106	
		crop.oilseed	1.101	1.021	1.184	
		crop.vegetable	1.035	0.923	1.159	
		intercept	adj.control	0.888	0.581	1.362
			adj.herb	0.834	0.561	1.253
			adj.woody	0.788	0.521	1.201
			crop.cereal	0.888	0.581	1.362
			crop.legume	0.829	0.510	1.359
			crop.maize	0.916	0.565	1.544
varying	study	crop.oilseed	0.849	0.547	1.329	
		crop.vegetable	1.059	0.609	1.806	
		cor.intercept:distance	-0.066	-0.523	0.403	
		sd.distance	0.867	0.573	1.250	
		sd.intercept	1.023	0.767	1.374	
		study:site	cor.intercept:distance	-0.259	-0.569	0.209
	sd.distance		0.542	0.082	0.874	
	sd.intercept		0.826	0.770	0.883	
	summary		R2	0.587	0.491	0.691

Table S9 Marginal estimates for distance slopes

Table S9: Marginal estimates for distance slopes with median, 95% credible interval (CI), percent change in the response per 10 m within-field distance and the probability of the slope being positive and negative calculated from the posterior sample across all crops and adjacent habitat types (translated to percent). Probabilities above 95% are highlighted in bold.

model	crop / habitat	median estimate	95% CI	median change per 10 m [%]	95% CI change per 10 m [%]	probability of positive slope [%]	probability of negative slope [%]
<i>richness (overall)</i>							
	overall	0.958	[0.870; 1.011]	-4.20	[-13.02; 1.07]	5.073	94.927
	cereal	0.968	[0.952; 0.983]	-3.16	[-4.80; -1.69]	0	100
	legume	0.982	[0.940; 1.026]	-1.80	[-6.04; 2.55]	20.85	79.150
	maize	0.905	[0.857; 0.957]	-9.50	[-14.35; -4.25]	0.025	99.975
	oilseed	0.963	[0.942; 0.984]	-3.70	[-5.77; -1.56]	0.050	99.95
	vegetable	0.926	[0.868; 0.989]	-7.39	[-13.21; -1.09]	1.125	98.875
	control	0.953	[0.924; 0.982]	-4.70	[-7.58; -1.77]	0.075	99.925
	herbaceous	0.951	[0.928; 0.973]	-4.93	[-7.18; -2.74]	0	100
	woody	0.942	[0.917; 0.967]	-5.84	[-8.30; -3.30]	0	100
<i>richness (carnivorous)</i>							
	overall	0.966	[0.852; 1.036]	-3.36	[-14.8; 3.6]	14.538	85.463
	cereal	0.978	[0.960; 0.993]	-2.24	[-4.02; -0.71]	0.225	99.775
	legume	0.995	[0.944; 1.048]	-0.51	[-5.64; 4.81]	42.575	57.425
	maize	0.888	[0.835; 0.946]	-11.16	[-16.53; -5.42]	0	100
	oilseed	0.964	[0.941; 0.988]	-3.57	[-5.85; -1.19]	0.3125	99.688
	vegetable	0.962	[0.893; 1.036]	-3.79	[-10.65; 3.62]	15.425	84.575
	control	0.967	[0.936; 1.004]	-3.03	[-6.43; 0.43]	4.05	95.95
	herbaceous	0.958	[0.934; 0.983]	-4.17	[-6.58; -1.72]	0.075	99.925
	woody	0.942	[0.915; 0.969]	-5.80	[-8.54; -3.07]	0.0125	99.988
<i>richness (omnivorous)</i>							
	overall	1.027	[0.913; 1.204]	2.72	[-8.67; 20.42]	70.471	29.529
	cereal	1.033	[0.998; 1.071]	3.30	[-0.20; 7.10]	96.588	3.413
	legume	1.012	[0.924; 1.104]	1.25	[-7.60; 10.40]	60.638	39.363
	maize	1.121	[1.004; 1.249]	12.09	[0.40; 24.90]	97.950	2.050
	oilseed	1.005	[0.950; 1.060]	0.49	[-5.00; 6.00]	57.188	42.813
	vegetable	1.006	[0.878; 1.157]	0.64	[-12.20; 15.70]	53.850	46.150
	control	1.043	[0.970; 1.119]	4.26	[-3.00; 11.90]	88.050	11.950
	herbaceous	1.017	[0.969; 1.069]	1.71	[-3.10; 6.90]	75.338	24.663
	woody	1.044	[0.980; 1.110]	4.37	[-2.00; 11.00]	91.000	9.000
<i>richness (omnivorous – without P. cupreus)</i>							
	overall	0.961	[0.813; 1.143]	-3.89	[-18.60; 14.26]	30.789	69.211
	cereal	0.976	[0.906; 1.046]	-2.39	[-9.40; 4.59]	25.163	74.839
	legume	0.956	[0.819; 1.112]	-4.43	[-18.10; 11.23]	27.538	72.463
	maize	1.013	[0.871; 1.184]	1.34	[-12.90; 18.42]	57.088	42.913
	oilseed	0.909	[0.804; 1.022]	-9.11	[-19.60; 2.23]	5.638	94.363
	vegetable	0.956	[0.815; 1.119]	-4.41	[-18.50; 11.94]	29.238	70.763
	control	0.960	[0.867; 1.059]	-3.96	[-13.30; 5.87]	22.175	77.825
	herbaceous	0.951	[0.872; 1.037]	-4.86	[-12.80; 3.69]	11.725	88.275
	woody	0.973	[0.853; 1.105]	-2.66	[-14.70; 10.54]	33.500	66.500
<i>richness (granivorous)</i>							
	overall	0.918	[0.797; 1.009]	-8.16	[-20.33; 0.91]	3.905	96.095
	cereal	0.914	[0.878; 0.951]	-8.55	[-12.21; -4.86]	0	100
	legume	0.950	[0.878; 1.025]	-4.97	[-12.20; 2.49]	9.025	90.975
	maize	0.867	[0.778; 0.97]	-13.26	[-22.24; -2.96]	0.525	99.475
	oilseed	0.953	[0.907; 1.004]	-4.71	[-9.30; 0.44]	3.450	96.550
	vegetable	0.876	[0.786; 0.981]	-12.39	[-21.39; -1.90]	1.025	98.975
	control	0.913	[0.862; 0.971]	-8.66	[-13.83; -2.88]	0.175	99.825
	herbaceous	0.912	[0.866; 0.955]	-8.84	[-13.44; -4.53]	0.075	99.925
	woody	0.909	[0.855; 0.974]	-9.06	[-14.49; -2.61]	0.425	99.575
<i>activity density (overall)</i>							
	overall	1.008	[0.876; 1.107]	0.84	[-12.37; 10.67]	56.588	43.412
	cereal	1.022	[0.995; 1.048]	2.25	[-0.47; 4.83]	94.950	5.050
	legume	1.047	[0.981; 1.123]	4.75	[-1.95; 12.35]	91.025	8.975
	maize	0.925	[0.857; 0.996]	-7.55	[-14.34; -0.40]	1.975	98.025
	oilseed	1.021	[0.98; 1.064]	2.13	[-1.99; 6.38]	84.250	15.750
	vegetable	0.993	[0.911; 1.086]	-0.71	[-8.94; 8.61]	43.475	56.525
	control	1.015	[0.961; 1.067]	1.53	[-3.86; 6.67]	70.350	29.650
	herbaceous	0.975	[0.942; 1.01]	-2.47	[-5.76; 0.98]	8.000	92.000
	woody	1.014	[0.971; 1.058]	1.38	[-2.90; 5.85]	72.500	27.500

<i>activity density (carnivorous)</i>						
overall	0.991	[0.866; 1.089]	-0.92	[-13.40; 8.90]	41.435	58.565
cereal	0.999	[0.969; 1.027]	-0.06	[-3.10; 2.70]	48.500	51.500
legume	1.013	[0.938; 1.094]	1.28	[-6.22; 9.36]	63.000	37.000
maize	0.916	[0.845; 0.995]	-8.37	[-15.55; -0.52]	1.900	98.100
oilseed	1.008	[0.964; 1.055]	0.79	[-3.64; 5.53]	63.438	36.563
vegetable	0.993	[0.905; 1.091]	-0.67	[-9.48; 9.10]	44.275	55.725
control	1.012	[0.958; 1.066]	1.23	[-4.18; 6.59]	66.450	33.550
herbaceous	0.975	[0.937; 1.013]	-2.53	[-6.33; 1.26]	9.213	90.788
woody	0.967	[0.926; 1.017]	-3.03	[-7.41; 1.70]	9.288	90.713
<i>activity density (omnivorous)</i>						
overall	1.104	[0.947; 1.293]	10.44	[-5.33; 29.30]	91.087	8.913
cereal	1.102	[1.044; 1.163]	10.24	[4.40; 16.30]	99.963	0.038
legume	1.140	[1.036; 1.259]	14.01	[3.60; 25.90]	99.638	0.363
maize	1.046	[0.928; 1.171]	4.64	[-7.20; 17.10]	77.988	22.013
oilseed	1.136	[1.052; 1.223]	13.64	[5.20; 22.30]	99.950	0.050
vegetable	1.115	[0.961; 1.290]	11.50	[-3.90; 29.00]	92.850	7.150
control	1.089	[1.005; 1.177]	8.86	[0.50; 17.70]	98.188	1.813
herbaceous	1.062	[0.994; 1.136]	6.19	[-0.60; 13.60]	96.313	3.688
woody	1.176	[1.078; 1.276]	17.64	[7.80; 27.60]	99.988	0.013
<i>activity density (omnivorous – without P. cupreus)</i>						
overall	1.006	[0.862; 1.176]	0.58	[-13.80; 17.59]	53.233	46.767
cereal	1.011	[0.951; 1.079]	1.15	[-4.90; 7.90]	63.813	36.188
legume	1.008	[0.868; 1.175]	0.81	[-13.20; 17.52]	54.313	45.688
maize	1.027	[0.898; 1.178]	2.72	[-10.20; 17.79]	65.375	34.625
oilseed	1.012	[0.904; 1.135]	1.20	[-9.60; 13.50]	58.438	41.563
vegetable	0.975	[0.839; 1.133]	-2.50	[-16.10; 13.35]	36.513	63.488
control	1.020	[0.930; 1.125]	2.04	[-7.00; 12.52]	66.475	33.525
herbaceous	0.976	[0.906; 1.055]	-2.43	[-9.40; 5.53]	26.438	73.563
woody	1.024	[0.912; 1.153]	2.39	[-8.80; 15.26]	66.038	33.963
<i>activity density (granivorous)</i>						
overall	0.946	[0.825; 1.035]	-5.41	[-17.55; 3.47]	9.960	90.040
cereal	0.950	[0.925; 0.975]	-5.04	[-7.51; -2.48]	0.025	99.975
legume	0.983	[0.917; 1.059]	-1.74	[-8.35; 5.93]	32.000	68.000
maize	0.907	[0.827; 0.992]	-9.26	[-17.27; -0.76]	1.725	98.275
oilseed	0.964	[0.926; 1.005]	-3.57	[-7.36; 0.55]	4.125	95.875
vegetable	0.887	[0.802; 0.979]	-11.29	[-19.78; -2.06]	0.950	99.050
control	0.919	[0.875; 0.969]	-8.09	[-12.46; -3.08]	0.100	99.900
herbaceous	0.952	[0.917; 0.987]	-4.82	[-8.31; -1.28]	0.425	99.575
woody	0.942	[0.900; 0.989]	-5.83	[-10.05; -1.09]	0.975	99.025
<i>activity density of small species (< 6 mm)</i>						
overall	0.960	[0.819; 1.056]	-3.98	[-18.07; 5.62]	19.723	80.277
cereal	0.966	[0.927; 1.001]	-3.41	[-7.33; 0.07]	2.800	97.200
legume	0.972	[0.885; 1.069]	-2.80	[-11.49; 6.92]	27.925	72.075
maize	0.871	[0.792; 0.955]	-12.95	[-20.75; -4.46]	0.175	99.825
oilseed	0.990	[0.936; 1.049]	-0.99	[-6.43; 4.89]	36.050	63.950
vegetable	0.958	[0.868; 1.059]	-4.25	[-13.15; 5.94]	19.825	80.175
control	0.957	[0.897; 1.016]	-4.26	[-10.29; 1.56]	8.100	91.900
herbaceous	0.950	[0.904; 0.996]	-5.01	[-9.56; -0.44]	1.450	98.550
woody	0.944	[0.888; 0.999]	-5.60	[-11.23; -0.10]	2.300	97.700
<i>activity density of medium-sized species (6 – 10 mm)</i>						
overall	0.976	[0.871; 1.076]	-2.43	[-12.87; 7.58]	30.218	69.783
cereal	0.991	[0.964; 1.016]	-0.92	[-3.55; 1.57]	23.375	76.625
legume	0.944	[0.876; 1.018]	-5.59	[-12.42; 1.84]	6.963	93.038
maize	0.999	[0.911; 1.095]	-0.08	[-8.89; 9.51]	49.263	50.738
oilseed	0.989	[0.950; 1.033]	-1.09	[-5.04; 3.26]	30.088	69.913
vegetable	0.947	[0.854; 1.055]	-5.26	[-14.58; 5.5]	16.300	83.700
control	0.968	[0.918; 1.019]	-3.22	[-8.20; 1.90]	11.100	88.900
herbaceous	0.952	[0.915; 0.990]	-4.76	[-8.53; -0.95]	0.888	99.113
woody	1.002	[0.957; 1.056]	0.20	[-4.35; 5.62]	53.025	46.975
<i>activity density of large species (> 10 mm)</i>						
overall	1.048	[0.908; 1.168]	4.83	[-9.21; 16.82]	76.333	23.667
cereal	1.057	[1.012; 1.104]	5.69	[1.20; 10.45]	99.340	0.660
legume	1.090	[1.003; 1.185]	8.97	[0.32; 18.55]	97.920	2.080
maize	0.978	[0.887; 1.073]	-2.21	[-11.25; 7.31]	31.750	68.250
oilseed	1.079	[1.014; 1.148]	7.90	[1.38; 14.84]	99.040	0.960
vegetable	1.014	[0.912; 1.130]	1.43	[-8.85; 12.97]	60.430	39.570
control	1.064	[0.996; 1.134]	6.44	[-0.36; 13.37]	96.820	3.180
herbaceous	1.015	[0.962; 1.071]	1.52	[-3.80; 7.10]	71.120	28.880
woody	1.050	[0.985; 1.120]	4.95	[-1.47; 11.95]	93.280	6.720

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